

REPORT

Supporting Mobile Student Accommodation Needs: An Implementation Model for Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE) Goals and Inter-Institutional Agreements (IIAs)

This paper was created in the framework of the Erasmus+ Key Action 2 project: Home of Mobile Europeans - HOME Squared: KA220-HED-3DA46644.

Project Coordinator: Politecnico di Milano

Project Partners: the Erasmus Student Network, the European University Foundation, the University of Oviedo, the International Union of Property Owners (UIPI) and Housing Anywhere.

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Title: Supporting Mobile Student Accommodation Needs: An Implementation Model for Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE) Goals and Inter-Institutional Agreements (IIAs)

Published by: Erasmus Student Network International AISBL

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Funded by
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Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Executive Summary

The effects of the on-going housing crisis in Europe have become increasingly widespread, negatively impacting various segments of society. Students participating in mobilities abroad are a particularly vulnerable group within this context as they often have to secure accommodation at their host destination remotely, navigating through challenging foreign housing markets. It is therefore more important than ever for higher education institutions (HEIs) that participate in the Erasmus+ programme to play a strong role in actively supporting students in finding accommodation for their mobility abroad, as they are required to do under the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE). The upcoming Erasmus+ programme cycle for 2028-2034 provides a fresh opportunity for the ECHE (and its associated tools), as well as inter-institutional agreements (IIAs), to be revised in this regard.

Policy recommendations in this report have been developed within the context of the HOME Squared project¹ (thehomeproject.eu) with the goal of forming an implementation model for further enhancing the realisation of the ECHE goals and IIAs for HEIs across Europe when it comes to assisting Erasmus+ participants in their search for accommodation abroad. These policy recommendations are aimed at various stakeholders who play an important role in ECHE implementation or monitoring, namely the European Commission, Erasmus+ National Agencies, and HEIs. The recommendations were largely developed on the basis of previous research conducted by the HOME Squared project on the topic of HEI support in housing provision for students and student experiences in the context of the housing crisis in Europe.

The first set of policy recommendations specifically touch on the revision of charter tools (namely the ECHE Guidelines, the ECHE Monitoring Guide, and the Erasmus Policy Statement) in order to make it clearer for HEIs as to what is expected of them regarding the accommodation support that needs to be provided to Erasmus+ participants, as well as for Erasmus+ National Agencies to improve their monitoring of the implementation of this ECHE principle. The second set of policy recommendations revolve around Erasmus+ tools that are not explicitly related to the ECHE (namely the Online Language Support Platform, the Erasmus+ Participant Report Form,, the Erasmus+ App, and Erasmus+ grants) and how they can be leveraged to better assist Erasmus+ participants in their accommodation search. The third and final set of policy recommendations look at how HEIs can engage in strategic partnerships to improve the quality of their accommodation services for Erasmus+ participants, specifically looking at collaboration with student associations and participation in the European Housing Alliance.

¹ HOME Squared (2023-2026) is an EU-funded project aimed at enhancing the housing experiences of students, with a focus on creating inclusive and supportive environments. Project partners include: Erasmus Student Network, European University Foundation, University of Oviedo, International Union of Property Owners, and Housing Anywhere.

INTRODUCTION

Introduction

Europe's Housing Crisis, its Impact on Students, and Recent EU Policy Developments

As students continue to be impacted by the housing crisis that has been brewing in Europe over the last decade, there has been a significant political shift from housing being seen as a strictly national-level issue to it becoming integrated as a core element of EU policy. Rent prices within the EU have increased by 25% between 2010 and 2024, while house prices have more than doubled in the same period (Eurostat, 2025). Limited housing supply is typically considered one of the “key drivers” behind the crisis (European Parliament, 2026-a, para.9).

To address the housing crisis in Europe, various actions have recently been taken at the EU level. To start off, in September 2024, Dan Jørgensen was appointed as the first-ever Commissioner on Energy and Housing, with this move serving as a clear indication that the issue of housing now has a place among the top of EU priorities. The Commissioner on Energy and Housing serves as a key figure in framing policy narrative regarding the housing crisis in Europe, with Jørgensen often emphasising the link between housing, democracy, and human rights, as well as highlighting vulnerable groups who are particularly affected (including students) (Jørgensen, 2025; Euronews, 2025). To assist the Commissioner on Energy and Housing in the implementation of the European Affordable Housing Plan (discussed in more detail below), as well as other actions set out in the Commissioner's mission letter, a Housing Taskforce was activated in February 2025.

Several months after appointing Commissioner on Energy and Housing, the European Commission unveiled its European Affordable Housing Plan, marking an important moment where housing took “centre stage” for the first time within EU policy (Quinn, 2026, para.1). The European Affordable Housing Plan, whose purpose is to propose “a series of concrete actions to help tackle the structural causes of [...] [the housing] crisis”, is built upon 4 pillars: boosting housing supply, mobilising investment, enabling immediate support while driving reforms, and protecting those most affected by the crisis (European Commission, 2025, p.1). Key actions featured in the plan include, for example, measures tackling the short-term rental market and boosting the construction sector, as well as the establishment of the European Housing Alliance and the European Housing Summit (European Commission, 2025). Additionally, it is important to note that the European Affordable Housing Plan makes several explicit references to students as a key group that needs to be addressed in the context of the housing crisis. This is directly emphasised in one of the plan's goals- to “[i]mprove access to housing for young people, students, apprentices and trainees” (European Commission, 2025, p.16).

Specifically regarding the case of mobile students, housing forms an essential component of their Erasmus+ mobilities, with accommodation needs being closely tied to the length of the specific mobility programme that they participate in. When it comes to short-term mobility, Erasmus+ Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs), for example, require students to secure accommodation anywhere from 5 to 30 days during the physical component of the programme. As for long-term mobility, Erasmus+ mobilities for studies or traineeships require students to ensure that they have accommodation for anywhere between 2 and 12 months. As for Erasmus Mundus programmes, they represent a unique (but challenging) case in which students need to find new accommodation every 6 months throughout the span of 2 years.

Despite its importance, accommodation is regularly cited as one of the most common issues that students experience in the context of their mobility abroad (Dias et al., 2024). Starting off with financial challenges, nearly half of students report paying more than €400 per month for their accommodation during their mobility abroad (Lepore et al., 2025). Overall, half of students were only able to cover less than 50% of their accommodation costs with scholarships (ESN & ESU, 2023). Further contributing to financial challenges is the fact that the majority of students also indicate having to pay a security deposit to secure their accommodation (Lepore et al., 2025). From a regulatory perspective, it is also important to note that non-EU students also face additional complications when it comes to securing accommodation due to visa procedures.

Moreover, within the backdrop of the housing crisis, the unique situation of mobile students having to typically secure their accommodation remotely also makes them particularly vulnerable to scams. In fact, over half reported that they confirmed their accommodation more than 30 days before arrival at the host destination (European Student Union & Erasmus Student Network, 2023). In the end, about a third of students report having encountered scams during their mobility experience (Lepore et al., 2025). The most common types of scams are related to fake accommodation listings (17.8%), overpayment of the accommodation (17.7%), and false quality standards (15.1%) (Lepore et al., 2025). Within this context, it is essential to note that student satisfaction with support provided by HEIs appears to be positively correlated with having them experiencing fewer scams (European Student Union & Erasmus Student Network, 2023).

More specifically, regarding accommodation services provided by HEIs, students tend to report low satisfaction rates- the average student satisfaction rate from the 15th edition of the ESNsurvey was 2.67/5 for accommodation services provided by host universities (Dias et al., 2024). This score is significantly lower compared to other types of services provided by host universities (Dias et al., 2024). Among students who did receive institutional support in finding accommodation for their mobility abroad, the most common type of support

received was HEIs providing accommodation information via their websites (Lepore et al., 2025). More active support measures, such as putting students directly in contact with housing providers, was significantly less widespread (Lepore et al., 2025).

In the end, securing accommodation can “make or break” whether students end up carrying out a mobility abroad, with approximately 5% of students indicating that they had to cancel their mobility due to housing-related barriers (Lepore et al., 2025). This highlights to what extent the housing crisis can directly negatively impact students’ educational experiences and future professional trajectories.

The ECHE and HEIs’ Role in Student Accommodation

All HEIs located in Erasmus+ programme countries who wish to participate in the programme’s activities are required to hold an ECHE. As of February 2026, over 6,000 HEIs within and beyond the EU have been awarded this certification, highlighting its large-scale uptake (European Commission, n.d.-b). The ECHE represents an important tool for HEIs- over 60% of HEIs found that it was useful for “enhancing the quality of [...] [their] institution’s internationalisation activities” (European University Association, 2025, p.47). The monitoring of compliance with the ECHE principles among HEIs is a role given to Erasmus+ National Agencies. In case serious breaches by HEIs are identified by Erasmus+ National Agencies, the ECHE can be revoked.

Specifically regarding accommodation, the ECHE assigns HEIs the responsibility to “[p]rovide active support to incoming mobile participants throughout the process of finding accommodation” (European Commission, n.d.-c). Nonetheless, HEIs currently face significant obstacles when it comes to the implementation of this ECHE principle. This is best reflected in the fact that 30% of students report not receiving any type of institutional support for finding accommodation (Lepore et al., 2025).

Furthermore, accommodation support for students remains structurally fragmented at HEIs in Europe. Almost half of HEIs report not having a centralised administrative service/unit to attend to student accommodation needs while nearly three quarters of IROs report not being directly involved in managing university accommodation services (Del Valle Tuero, 2025). This type of fragmentation can negatively impact the way in which accommodation services are delivered to mobile students (Del Valle Tuero, 2025).

Various factors also hinder HEIs’ ability to directly provide students with access to public student accommodation. For example, the main market-related challenges that IROs identify when it comes to the public student accommodation sector are excess demand (31.0%), inflation and rising costs (15.9%), and budget constraints (13.1%) (Del Valle Tuero, 2025). This is further complicated by knowledge gaps that are widespread among IROs regarding

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different types of available policy support mechanisms for student housing (Del Valle Tuero, 2025).

**POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
ON STRENGTHENING THE IMPLEMENTATION
OF ECHE GOALS AND IIAS
TO IMPROVE STUDENT
ACCOMMODATION SUPPORT**

Policy Recommendations on Strengthening the Implementation of ECHE Goals and IIAs to Improve Student Accommodation Support

ECHE and IIA tools should be revised in order to make it clearer for HEIs as to what is expected of them regarding the accommodation support being provided to Erasmus+ participants, as well as to improve Erasmus+ National Agencies' monitoring of the implementation of this ECHE principle.

1. ECHE Guidelines

The ECHE Guidelines document aims to provide HEIs with more detailed information regarding the ECHE principles and what their implementation could mean in practice before, during, and after mobility. This includes explaining what is meant when the ECHE states that HEIs need to “provide active support to incoming mobile participants throughout the process of finding accommodation” (European Commission, n.d.-c, p.2). The first step to ensuring a stronger implementation of the ECHE by HEIs is revising the ECHE Guidelines document to offer more clarity as to what the minimum expected standards are when it comes to the accommodation support being provided by HEIs.

To start off, the ECHE Guidelines document states that regarding accommodation, “[i]f students experience fraud or discrimination, the HEI/enterprise/organisation should offer guidance and support to overcome the issue” (European Commission, 2020, p.17). However, no further explanation is given to HEIs as to how they are actually expected to support Erasmus+ participants in such situations. This is relevant considering how frequently students encounter scams while searching for accommodation for their mobility abroad. Therefore, a revision of this section of the ECHE Guidelines document to include specific examples of services aimed at helping Erasmus+ participants who have fallen victim to fraud or have experienced discrimination can help better guide HEIs in this regard. This could be done in a similar way to which the guidelines already currently explain different types of accommodation information that HEIs could upload on their websites to better assist students. Below are examples of services that could be included in this section of the ECHE Guidelines document.

Temporary emergency accommodation: In cases where mobile students fall victim to scams, they can suddenly end up without secure housing at the host destination (where they often lack the social contacts needed to find support). By providing or helping students secure temporary emergency accommodation, HEIs can serve as an important lifeline when such

situations occur. This could be done by, for example, HEIs creating a database of host family volunteers in the area or actively collaborating with NGOs that do work on this issue.

Informal legal advice: Mobile students are at an increased risk of not being aware of their rights when it comes to renting accommodation during their mobility abroad. HEIs can offer informal legal advice to support students when it comes to taking action in case of accommodation scams or discrimination. This could be implemented at HEIs, for instance, by contacting professors within law faculties and creating an online registration form where students can schedule consultation sessions with them. The professors' participation could be incentivised by HEIs via implementation of workload compensation (i.e. the hours they spend giving legal advice to students can be converted into time off).

Foreign language support: Mobile students are often left to navigate housing markets in destinations where they do not speak the local language(s). This can limit their ability to apply to accommodation listings that are only published in the local language(s) of the host destination. Furthermore, it can also be challenging for them to effectively communicate any concerns or complaints with their landlords due to language barriers. HEIs can step in here by providing targeted foreign language support to mobile students to address such challenges, which could be done in a similar way as described above regarding legal advice.

Furthermore, when the ECHE Guidelines document mentions various kinds of accommodation information that could be provided to Erasmus+ participants via the HEIs' websites, it is important to note that there is no explicit mention when it comes to presenting such information in an accessible way for students. Even if HEIs provide detailed and relevant information, this loses its effectiveness if it is difficult for students to find or understand it. Consequently, the European Commission should consider specifically adding in this section of the ECHE Guidelines document a point highlighting the need for accommodation information to be accessible for Erasmus+ participants. Example of actions could be included to guide HEIs in this respect are:

- Avoiding the use of lengthy blocks of uninterrupted texts when presenting accommodation information on webpages and instead implementing the frequent use of headers and/or bullet points in order to make it easier for students to absorb
- Ensuring that all accommodation information is centralised in as few webpages as possible in order to allow students to navigate better
- Avoiding the use of jargon (especially regional-based terms- e.g. T1/T2/T3 in France) when presenting accommodation information without providing definitions in order to make it easier for students to understand

- Creating infographic visuals and/or videos to highlight the most important accommodation information in order to present it in a more engaging way for students
- Ensuring that all accommodation information on webpages is translated into English (and if possible other relevant languages)

Additionally, another point to potentially consider adding to the ECHE Guidelines document would be to explicitly encourage HEIs to regularly check that the accommodation information that they are providing via their websites is accurate and up-to-date. This can be implemented similarly as to how it is currently being done in the guidelines when it comes to course catalogues, where it asks HEIs to “[p]ublish and regularly update the course catalogue on the website of the Institution well in advance of the mobility periods, so as to be transparent to all parties and allow mobile students to make well-informed choices” (European Commission, 2020, p.12).

2. ECHE Monitoring Guide

The ECHE Monitoring Guide serves as an important tool for Erasmus+ National Agencies to monitor whether HEIs in their country are being compliant with the principles of the ECHE. It includes evaluation criteria regarding core mobility principles², credit recognition, inclusion, and digitalisation (European Commission, 2023-b). The current version of the ECHE Monitoring Guide has only one evaluation criteria explicitly related to accommodation support for Erasmus+ participants, which is evaluation criterion 4.4 “Accessibility and provision of assistance in search of accommodation” (European Commission, 2023-b, p.33). In order to score strongly on this evaluation criterion, HEIs need to show that “80-100% of incoming students are satisfied or very satisfied with the accommodation assistance provided” to them (European Commission, 2023-b, p.34). While this serves as an important evaluation criterion, by itself, it does not provide the whole picture regarding the accommodation services being offered by HEIs to Erasmus+ participants.

To start off, student satisfaction with accommodation services is a purely subjective evaluation criteria when it comes to assessing the quality of such services. This is particularly important to consider within the context that Erasmus+ participants might not even be aware that HEIs have the responsibility to help them find accommodation due to the ECHE. Additionally, student satisfaction rates are also not necessarily a reflection of how accessible those accommodation services are.

Therefore, to address this point, additional objective evaluation criteria regarding the accommodation services provided by HEIs can be included in the ECHE Monitoring Guide by

² The term “core mobility principles” refers to elements regarding the course catalogue, recognition, grading systems, credit transfer and grade conversion, and student support.

the European Commission. Such evaluation criteria could be related to the extensiveness of accommodation services (e.g. what is the coverage of the different types of accommodation services that the HEI provides to Erasmus+ participants and does it accurately reflect the actual needs of the participants?), access to accommodation services (e.g. how long do Erasmus+ participants have to wait in order to get access to different types of accommodation services at the HEI and how simple is the process for getting access to those services?), and proactiveness in sharing information about accommodation services with Erasmus+ participants (e.g. how do HEIs directly communicate with students to share information about accommodation services?). It is important to mention that while this point is somewhat addressed in the current ECHE Monitoring Guide in evaluation criteria 4.5 “Provision of and information on student support and services”, evaluation criteria 4.5 does not effectively address issues experienced by HEIs when it comes to providing accommodation information due to how general it is. Therefore, it would be more beneficial to have evaluation criteria 4.5 be split instead into multiple evaluation criteria based on themes (i.e. accommodation, visa, and insurance).

Furthermore, it is important to note that no evaluation criteria are included in the ECHE Monitoring Guide that specifically assess what type of accommodation information HEIs publish on their websites. Nonetheless, as previously emphasised, ensuring that Erasmus+ participants have access to such information constitutes an important first step to ensuring that they have a quality mobility experience abroad and should therefore represent a central element when it comes to the evaluation criteria. Evaluation criteria regarding this point could relate to whether information is included on the institutional website regarding typical rental practices in the area (e.g. standard prices, rental contracts, accommodation types in the area, etc.), accommodation scams that have previously occurred in the area, and the contact details of trusted landlords/housing providers in the area.

Lastly, the points discussed above could also be incorporated into the “Annex 1: Sample questions” section of the ECHE Monitoring Guide, which includes interview questions that Erasmus+ National Agencies can ask while conducting site visits at HEIs to monitor ECHE compliance (European Commission, 2023-b). Currently, this section of the guide only includes two questions that are explicitly linked to accommodation (European Commission, 2023-b, p.29-30):

1. “Do you have a system in place to support incoming students in their research for accommodation?” (for staff to answer)
2. “What specific information and support did you receive from your receiving institution before and during your mobility (on accommodation, student support and services, insurance and visa if applicable)?” (for students to answer)

More questions could be added in this annex in order to further guide Erasmus+ National Agencies in their monitoring. Regarding the questions aimed at HEI staff, there are currently none that look at the accommodation information that their institution provides to Erasmus+ participants. A question like *How you ensure that accommodation information is accessible and easy to understand for Erasmus+ participants?* could be added in order to address this gap. As for the questions aimed at students, none address the ease of access and/or utility of the accommodation services being provided, meaning that questions like *Did you find it easy to access accommodation services provided by your host institution?* and *To what extent do you think that the services provided by your host institution supported you in finding accommodation?* could also be added to the annex.

3. ECHE Self-Assessment Tool

The ECHE Self-Assessment Tool allows rectors and vice rectors/chancellors, as well as IROs/Erasmus+ coordinators, to see to what extent their HEIs are embodying the principles of the ECHE. In the current version of the tool aimed specifically at IROs/Erasmus+ coordinators, there are only two statements that they can check-off when it comes to explicitly supporting Erasmus+ participants with finding accommodation (European Commission, n.d.-d):

1. “Clear and comprehensive information on the institutional website on accommodation options available sufficiently in advance of the mobility”
2. “Assistance for incoming participants in finding accommodation, e.g. through cooperation with the local student organisations”

Regarding the first statement, the phrase “clear and comprehensive information” is highly subjective to the IRO/Erasmus+ coordinators filling out the self-assessment tool (European Commission, n.d.-d). In other words, there is no clear way for them to objectively self-assess this evaluation point. Similarly, the second statement, while slightly more effective compared to the first due to the fact that it includes a concrete example, still does not allow IROs/Erasmus+ coordinators to accurately self-assess because it does not address, for example, how extensive the assistance being provided is or how easy it is for Erasmus+ students to access it. Therefore, the ECHE Self-Assessment Tool has room to be improved and can be revised by the European Commission to include more statements regarding the coverage of accommodation services the HEI provides for Erasmus+ participants (this way, IROs will be able to identify which services are still not currently being offered by the HEI), how easily accessible accommodation services provided by HEIs are for Erasmus+ participants, and whether the accommodation information on the HEI’s website is presented in an accessible way and is up to date.

4. Erasmus Policy Statement (and Other Internationalisation Strategy Documents)

One tool used by Erasmus+ National Agencies to monitor ECHE compliance is the Erasmus Policy Statement document that HEIs are required to submit within one month of being awarded the ECHE (European Commission, 2020). In this document, HEIs explain their internationalisation policy in detail. The current version of the Erasmus Policy Statement template does not include any questions that explicitly ask HEIs to outline how they plan to support Erasmus+ participants when it comes to accommodation. Instead, HEIs are only asked to generally describe the “support [they offer] for participants on mobility” (KU Leuven, n.d., p.4). This has led to HEIs not including important information regarding the type of accommodation support that they are committed to delivering in the document. Therefore, the Erasmus Policy Statement could be revised by the European Commission to explicitly request HEIs to address the issue of accommodation support.

At the institutional level, HEIs can consider ensuring that they dedicate time to analysing to what extent housing is actually incorporated within internationalisation strategy documents such as the Erasmus Policy Statement, as well as reflecting on ways to make it a central pillar of their internationalisation strategy. One way to ensure this would be to create a stronger link between partnership development and housing. In other words, internationalisation strategies could, for example, explicitly highlight prioritising collaboration with HEIs that are particularly strong at supporting students in their accommodation search. Furthermore, HEIs can also take time to evaluate whether any quantitative mobility targets that they set within their internationalisation strategies adequately align with the housing capacity in the area. This would help to minimise the possibility of Erasmus+ participants experiencing precarious housing situations. Lastly, HEIs could also ensure that their internationalisation strategy also incorporates actions when it comes to improving coordination between different actors within their institution on the issue of housing. This would help to address the challenges that HEIs face regarding fragmentation when it comes to the management of accommodation services, keeping in mind the fact that most IROs are not directly involved with these services (De Valle Tuero, 2025).

5. Erasmus+ IIA Templates

Currently, the European Commission provides on the Erasmus+ website templates that HEIs can use to create IIAs with other institutions abroad. These templates have been described as reflecting the “minimum programme requirements and rules” for IIAs, therefore serving as an important reference point for HEIs across the Erasmus+ programme countries and third countries associated with the programme (European Commission, 2023-a, p.4). Zooming in on the intra-European mobility IIA template, it includes a dedicated section on housing (see Figure 1). The information requested in this section regarding accommodation

is very limited, only referring to the contact details for HEI staff responsible for supporting students with securing accommodation and relevant website links. This current lack of detail expected in the template regarding accommodation represents an area of improvement as it can actively discourage IROs from putting in detailed information about the accommodation support that they officially agree to provide to mobile students coming to their institution.

Figure 1: Housing section in the Erasmus+ IIA template for intra-European mobility (European Commission, 2021-a)

Housing

The institution will guide incoming mobile participants in finding accommodation, according to the requirements of the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education. Information and assistance can be provided by the following contact points and information sources:

<Contact details> (email, phone)	Website for information

Therefore, the housing section in the template could be improved by requesting for HEIs to list what kind of accommodation services they offer to incoming Erasmus+ participants. This can be done in a similar way done in the inclusion and accessibility section of the template (see Figure 2). Specific types of services that could be listed as examples to help guide IROs can include (once again) providing updated list(s) of landlords/housing providers vetted by the HEI, offering informal legal consultations for rental contracts, securing temporary emergency accommodation, etc.

Figure 2: Inclusion and accessibility section in the Erasmus+ IIA template for intra-European mobility (European Commission, 2021-a)

Inclusion and accessibility

The institution will provide support to incoming mobile participants with fewer opportunities, according to the requirements of the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education. Information and assistance can be provided by the following contact points and information sources:

Available infrastructure adjusted for people with:	<Description of infrastructure>	<Contact details> (email, phone)	Website for information
[For example: - Reduced mobility - Hearing impairments - Visual impairments]			

Available support services for people with:	<Description of support services>	<Contact details> (email, phone)	Website for information
[For example: - Reduced mobility - Hearing impairments - Visual impairments]			

At the institutional level, HEIs could also consider taking some of the following actions when drafting IIAs with other institutions. To start off, HEIs can ensure that their factsheets (which are attached to IIAs) contain a detailed section on accommodation, taking into consideration relevant recommendations from this report. Furthermore, they could try to set early nomination deadlines in order to give students sufficient time to inform themselves about

how to secure accommodation in their host destination. Additionally, HEIs would horizontally benefit from dedicated channels to discuss common challenges and to exchange good practices, allowing them to assess with each other what the housing situation looks like in their respective areas. While the ECHE only mentions HEIs supporting incoming students when it comes to finding accommodation, such meetings would also allow IROs to improve the support they provide to outgoing students.

Erasmus+ tools or initiatives that are not explicitly related to the ECHE/IAs should be revised and leveraged in order for HEIs to better assist Erasmus+ participants in their accommodation search.

1. Online Language Support Platform

The Online Language Support (OLS) platform offers language modules in 29 languages to all Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps participants. Previously, students were typically required to sit a language test on the platform before and after mobility in order to receive the full Erasmus+ grant amount. Currently, language modules on the OLS platform focus on 10 domains: computer science, health and social care, logistics, mechanics, tourism, graphic design, agriculture, hair and beauty services, catering, and construction (European Commission, 2025). While the current version of the OLS platform does include videos related to accommodation, they tend to be limited to a tourism-based context (e.g. reserving a room at a youth hostel) and do not address the topic of long-term housing (EU Academy, n.d.).

Considering the large reach that the OLS platform has with Erasmus+ participants (over 2 million users had already used it to test their language skills by 2020), these language modules could be revisited by the European Commission in order to include dedicated sessions related to finding long-term accommodation (European Commission, 2021-b, p.26). These sessions could specifically include, for example, videos regarding typical rental practices, common accommodation scams, and tenant rights. Besides adding such videos onto the platform, the sessions could also include (as is currently being done within the language modules) interactive quizzes to test students' knowledge on these topics. Additionally, key vocabulary featured in the sessions could be developed with inspiration from Housing Glossary developed by HOME Squared's *Guidelines for Mobile Students on Housing* report (Ben Rommane, 2024). In the end, this update to the OLA platform would help better prepare Erasmus+ participants to navigate the housing market in their host destination.

2. Erasmus+ Participant Report Form

The Erasmus+ Participant Report Form is a questionnaire that Erasmus+ participants are requested to fill out after completing their mobility abroad, the results from which are often used as an important reference point on how the Erasmus+ programme can be improved in the future. To ensure a high number of respondents for the survey, filling out the form is typically conditional to students receiving their full Erasmus+ grant amount. Currently, the Erasmus+ Participant Report Form for KA1 student mobilities contains only one question that explicitly makes reference to accommodation by only vaguely asking Erasmus+ participants to assess their level of satisfaction with their accommodation support they received from the receiving institution (European Commission, 2026). Considering to what extent accommodation plays a crucial role in shaping Erasmus+ participants' experiences, questions related to the topic should be given greater priority in the Erasmus+ Participant Report Form. Adding such questions to the questionnaire could directly help both HEIs and the Erasmus+ National Agencies to better contribute to the implementation of the ECHE principles as more detailed data on Erasmus+ participants' experiences would pinpoint areas upon which HEIs could further improve upon when it comes to the accommodation services they provide. Examples of questions that could potentially be included in the questionnaire are:

- What type of accommodation services did your receiving institution provide you before, during, and after mobility?
- To what extent did the accommodation services that your receiving institution provide you with cover all your needs when it came to finding accommodation for your mobility abroad?
- How easy/difficult was it to access accommodation services from your receiving institution?

Figure 3: *Question referencing accommodation in the Erasmus+ Participant Report Form (European Commission, 2026)*

7.2 How satisfied were you with the support provided by your receiving institution?

	Very satisfied	Rather satisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Very dissatisfied	Not applicable
• Administrative support	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Academic support	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Social integration with the local students	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Engagement with the local community	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
• Guidance on how to find accommodation	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

3. Erasmus+ App

Launched in 2020, the Erasmus+ App aims to serve as “the single point of entry” for programme participants by centralising information relevant to the mobility experience ([European Commission, n.d.-a](#), para.1). The European University Association (2023)’s mid-term evaluation of the Erasmus+ programme found that 27% of HEI staff responded that they believed that it helped to facilitate student mobility to at least some extent, highlighting room for further development. To directly contribute to the improvement of the Erasmus+ App, the HOME Squared project has facilitated the integration of a housing search module within the application. This housing search module allows students to gain access to vetted housing providers and to filter accommodation options using quality labels developed by the project.

With this new boost in the Erasmus+ App’s utility, stronger action could now be taken by the European Commission and HEIs to increase students’ awareness about the application in order to better support them in their search for accommodation for their mobility abroad. Awareness could be raised by, for example, HEIs including information about the HOME Squared feature of the Erasmus+ App on institutional webpages related to accommodation, as well as in information sessions related to Erasmus+ mobilities.

4. Erasmus+ Grants

As previously mentioned, about 50% of students are not able to cover even half of their accommodation costs with scholarships and they often need to pay a security deposit prior to moving in (ESN & ESU, 2023; Lepore et al., 2025). When it comes to intra-European mobility, Erasmus+ grant amounts are given by HEIs to students based on the programme country where the mobility will be carried out (see Table 1). This grant distribution system does not take into consideration higher accommodation costs in large cities. To illustrate this with an example, a student doing their Erasmus+ study mobility in Paris (where the average

rent is 905 euros per month) will typically receive the same grant amount as a student doing theirs in Pau (where average rent is 383 euros per month) in France (L'Étudiant, 2025). In order to better support mobile students in securing accommodation in cities that are suffering acutely from the housing crisis and to ensure a more efficient usage of the Erasmus+ budget, the grant distribution system can be fine-tuned by the European Commission. Instead of Erasmus+ National Agencies setting the minimum and maximum grant amounts on the basis of the three groups of countries within the ranges set within the Erasmus+ guide, this could instead be done on the basis of the average cost of living within different cities. In order to implement such an approach, a database with the average living costs in different cities would need to be made available to ensure that the data is comparable.

Table 1: Erasmus+ grant distribution system by groups of countries (European Commission, 2026)

Group 1: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden
Group 2: Cyprus, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Latvia, Malta, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain
Group 3: Bulgaria, Croatia, Hungary, Lithuania, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Türkiye

Furthermore, stronger action needs to be taken by HEIs to ensure that students receive grants and scholarships as early as possible before they leave for mobility, as already encouraged in the ECHE (European Commission, n.d.-c). The 15th edition of the ESNsurvey revealed that only 37% of students reported having received their scholarship before departing to their host destination (Dias et al., 2024).

Specifically in the context of Erasmus+ grants, it is also important to consider that most students reported not receiving the full grant amount until after they returned from mobility experience (MEGA consortium, 2023). Also worth noting is that in terms of perception, students rarely identify themselves as being responsible for when late grant payment occurred- this responsibility was instead overwhelmingly assigned to home universities (MEGA consortium, 2023). This all contributes to significant financial stress for students, often leaving them to rely on personal finances or family support (which in turn makes Erasmus+ mobilities less accessible to individuals with fewer economic opportunities).

Moreover, it is also important to point out that many students experience significant administrative burden when applying for Erasmus+ grants. In fact, the majority indicate that

they needed to spend a few days to one week on paperwork in order to apply for one (MEGA consortium, 2023). This is worrying as it can severely demotivate students from participating in an Erasmus+ mobility in the first place. Consequently, in order to address this issue, HEIs should consider regularly conducting focus groups with students applying for Erasmus+ grants in order to gain a better understanding about what aspects of the application process is causing the most problems (and how it should be revised) and dedicate more time to reflecting on how to make the instructions for Erasmus+ grant applications more accessible and easier to understand (this could mean, for example, creating short informative videos on the Erasmus+ grant application process at the HEI instead of just having long instructional texts).

HEIs should engage in strategic partnerships to improve the quality of the accommodation services they provide to Erasmus+ participants.

1. Student Association-HEI Collaboration

Student associations, such as local sections of ESN, can play a vital role in helping Erasmus+ participants find accommodation for their mobility abroad. Nonetheless, they tend to operate with limited resources and entirely depend on the work volunteers. Consequently, it is important for student associations and HEIs to further strengthen collaboration in order to work together towards the better implementation of the ECHE goals. One way to do so is by HEIs investing in organising relevant training for volunteers. These trainings could relate to some of the following topics.

Training related to advocacy: Student associations can play an important role in campaigning for the construction of student accommodation with the leveraging of advocacy efforts of volunteers in supporting students to tackle housing-related issues. Training courses on the topic of advocacy offered by HEIs could help boost such efforts across Europe by having institutions share their expertise with volunteers regarding local political landscapes, strategic stakeholders and decision-makers, different advocacy approaches, debate and persuasion skills, etc.

Training related to research: The unique on-the-ground position of student associations make them fertile partners for HEIs when it comes to research on the accommodation experiences of students (which is essential to improving the services provided by the HEI). These training sessions could focus, for example, on survey methodology.

Training related to law: While sometimes serving as a first point of contact in cases where mobile students fall victim to accommodation scams, many volunteers at student associations do not have any kind of training to provide informal legal guidance on what

students can do in such situations. These trainings could focus on rental contacts, reporting/filing (legal) complaints, local tenant rights, etc.

In order to further increase the value of the training for the volunteers, microcredentials can be issued to them upon completion of the session(s). In the end, by investing in such training sessions for volunteers, HEIs can actively contribute to increasing the quality of accommodation services being provided by student associations to Erasmus+ students, thus strengthening ECHE implementation. These training sessions can also help to facilitate a better understanding between HEIs and student associations as to what kind of services each of them provide, which in turn could help identify any type of redundancy in the services being provided by both.

Furthermore, student associations can also work together with HEIs to further raise general awareness about the ECHE principles among Erasmus+ participants. This is especially important considering that 20% of students reported not being informed at all about their rights laid out in the Erasmus Student Charter (including receiving support for finding accommodation from HEIs) (Dias et al., 2024). By knowing their rights regarding accommodation services, students will become more empowered to approach HEIs to provide direct feedback on the services they receive from their host institution.

2. European Housing Alliance

As previously mentioned, the European Affordable Housing Plan calls for the establishment of a new European Housing Alliance, which will serve to promote “cooperation and sharing of good practice between Member States, cities, regions, other EU institutions and stakeholders” (European Commission, 2025, p.2). With it being planned to be launched at the upcoming EU Housing Summit in the third quarter of 2026, special measures can be taken to ensure that HEIs and student housing providers are given a key role within this alliance and to encourage their active participation within it. IROs at HEIs already report that they view collaboration and partnerships with local authorities as one of the main ways that they can mitigate market-related challenges when it comes to the public student accommodation sector (Del Valle Tuero, 2025). At the institutional level, HEIs can start reflecting on who could represent them at the European Housing Alliance, prepare informational material (e.g. reports, statistics) relevant to the topic of student housing, and convene with other HEIs to see how they can forge common positions.

Additionally, as the topic of digitalisation will be given particular focus within the European Housing Alliance, it is also essential for HEIs and student housing providers to share ideas and good practices regarding digital tools or improvements that can be made to support mobile students in securing accommodation in their host destination.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion

The ECHE serves a vital role when it comes to engaging HEIs in supporting Erasmus+ participants in their search for accommodation at their host destination during their mobility abroad. The importance of the ECHE in this regard has been further accentuated within the context of the current housing crisis taking place in Europe, where students are confronted with growing challenges when it comes to the affordability and quality of student accommodation, while being increasingly pushed towards competitive private housing markets where they are at greater risk of falling victim to scams.

However, the research conducted in the context of this report revealed that various tools being used by HEIs and Erasmus+ National Agencies to guide and/or monitor ECHE implementation are not currently able to provide the depth needed to effectively evaluate accommodation services being provided by HEIs to mobile students who are navigating this complex reality. This typically results in HEIs being left unsure as to where they stand when it comes to the extent to which they are adhering to the implementation of this ECHE principle, which in turn limits their ability to address and improve on any weak points they have in this area. Furthermore, it was also observed that other instruments of the Erasmus+ programme not directly related to the ECHE are also not being utilised to their full potential when it comes to addressing the housing needs of mobile students.

In the end, investing in improving ECHE implementation among HEIs (especially when it comes to accommodation services) can meaningfully contribute to increasing the total number of individuals that actually end up carrying out mobilities abroad and improving the overall quality of these mobility experiences. Without taking strong action to address accommodation challenges in the context of mobilities, it will not be possible to fully achieve the main objective of the proposal for the upcoming Erasmus+ programme cycle, which is to build “a resilient, competitive, and cohesive EU” (European Parliament, 2026-b, p.1).

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